

FEMALE LABOR MIGRATION AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO THE FAMILY ECONOMY

Sitti Nurtina

University of Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Indonesia

E-mail: sittinurtina10@gmail.com

Abstract: International migration occurs due to population growth that is not matched by growth in opportunities and job availability. Increased labor force and limited domestic employment, making the flow of labor migration abroad increased. International migration as labor is dominated by female workers (TKW). The increasing flow of labor migration of Indonesian women in abroad, even beyond men, shows the importance of understanding what is behind their movement. Especially women who are already married must have a reason to immigrate. For rural and married women who do not have many skills, international migration is a golden opportunity to improve their family's economy. This research is qualitative by using method of textual study by analyzing secondary data from various related literatures, then completed by semi structured interview with some main respondents that former female worker. Empirical data shows that married women working overseas due to economic considerations. Initiatives for work generally come from women themselves, whereas family members only approve. Thus, women have more freedom and confidence to decide to work overseas.

Keywords: migration; female labor; female workers; family economy

Introduction

Indonesia as a developing country is one of the countries with high international migration rate every year. Recorded Indonesia started sending migrant workers officially since 1970. The program was set to reduce the number of unemployed at the time.¹ The increasing demand for labor in developed countries and the availability of labor in developing countries is a factor that increases international migration activities. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Indonesia recorded approximately 3,091,284 Indonesian citizens currently abroad, of whom 58.9 percent work as domestic workers. The number of migrants can be estimated two to three times higher, as most

Indonesian citizens do not report to the Immigration Service.² Several countries including Indonesia, migrating labor are the main options for survival, especially for people in rural areas. Migration abroad is done as another alternative when weather changes disrupt agricultural production or economic crisis. Families in the village can survive by relying on remittances from families working abroad.

Every year, hundreds of thousands of Indonesians migrate to work as migrant workers. The majority of them are women, which is estimated as much as 72% of the total number of Indonesian Migrant workers (migrant worker). Of all the women migrant workers (migrant worker), 92% of them work as domestic workers. The average of female workers comes from different parts of Indonesia, especially from the villages. Indonesia is one of the sending countries of migrant workers, with the number of migrant workers especially women quite high. One of the main reasons for the increasing percentage of women laborers is that the patriarchal mode of development deprives women's resources, ultimately further strengthening the feminization of women's impoverishment.³ Most of the women who choose to work overseas are from the poorest regions of Indonesia. Unemployment, poverty, and the limitation of formal education are the contributing factors to the increasing number of Indonesian women emigrating, not to mention the opportunity to get relatively high salary compared to their villages.

During this time, social construction is understood to place women in the household domain with tasks or activities related to taking care of the household, husband and child. While, men are in the domain outside the household activities that focus on productive economy by earning money for the family in accordance with its role as head of the household. However, in the era of globalization women's involvement in economic activity is a crucial phenomenon. The involvement of women in the economic activities that earning, in this case the migration of women as overseas workers shows that women's activities already include economic activities outside the household. But there are things that should be considered by the prospective migrant worker is the choice between taking care of the household and working abroad as migrant workers. Women who come from the village especially from the middle to the bottom are all involved in the economic cycle. They left the village for the sake of improving the economy by finding alternative jobs. By looking at women's activeness in household economic strategies, it is clear how important the role of village women work for their family's survival.⁴ One of the strategies undertaken by village women about

earning a living to save the family economy is to do international migration, in other words being migrant workers.

Some recent studies show that in the migration process women are generally passive migrants, meaning to immigrate by following their husbands, parents (father), or brothers. Female migrant workers in the context of migration, since 1980s the proportion of women working abroad is considerable. Can be seen from the data of sending migrant workers several time periods revealed that the number of women sent abroad is greater than men. This can be seen from the sex ratio (Sex ratio: number of men per 100 women) of 47.5% in the period 1989-1994, 36% in the period 1994-2008, and by 77.6% in 2013 -2015.⁵ This situation indicates that there is a tendency migration of female migrant workers no longer dependent on migration of family brothers. However, women are also active migrants who migrate themselves to work abroad. Thus, this is a sign of the feminization of migrant workers, because the number of migrant workers working abroad has increased over men.⁶

Women in their development want to be self-reliant in development, with the role of transition as a workforce that actively participates in supplementing income by earning a living. Among the migrant workers who work abroad more women who have married status than unmarried women, and the majority come from the village. Being a female worker is considered the answer to get a higher family economic status. However, with the status of marriage, the role of domestic such as taking care of the household, children, and husband led to the decision of married women to work more complex. There are factors underlying why the percentages of married women more work abroad and why these migrant workers come from rural areas on average. Therefore, researchers are interested in doing research on the phenomenon of female labor migration and its contribution to family economics.

Methodology

The research approach used is descriptive qualitative approach. By using library research method, this data collection method is a technique of collecting secondary data where the data obtained are taken, analyzed, and quoted from various sources. Secondary data is data obtained not directly from the source of literature that support the proposal. This study uses secondary data, through scientific books or research results, documents, journals, articles, newspapers and other documents relevant to this research.

Then this research was completed by semi structured interview with some main respondents that former female worker.

Discussion

There are various approaches from experts who can explain the process of migration, such as the approach of economic theory,⁷ demographic and geographical approaches,⁸ and psychological approaches.⁹ According to research Wulan analyzing of migration process based on three theories. First, the neoclassical view of positive relationships between migration and development. Second, historical structures that tend to be more pessimist see the relationship between migration and development. The third theory is that bridging the two previous theories of migrants network that emphasizes the importance of social networks and households.¹⁰ Given the fact that the decision-making to immigrate at the individual level from a geographical perspective is influenced by four factors, namely: factors in the origin region; factors in the destination; migration barrier factors; and individual factors of migration.¹¹

Since a few decades ago, migration of labor migrants to work abroad has occurred even before Indonesian independence and still continues to this day. Generally, in destination countries TKI works as plantation laborers, laborers on development and construction projects, and small farmers.¹² Women working overseas become Female Workers based on the Decree of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration No. RI. Kep. 104 A / MEN / 2002 meant by Indonesian labor migrants is Indonesian citizens, both men and women working abroad in a certain period based on the division of labor through the procedure of placement of TKI, then what is meant by the household of TKW is household or family where wife works or has worked as an overseas migrant worker.¹³ Women's involvement in the public sector from year to year shows a steadily increasing number of women engaged in workplaces in various economic sectors.

In countries of origin of female migrant workers such as Indonesia and the Philippines, this labor dispatch has also become an important part of economic planning in order to reduce unemployment pressure and increase foreign exchange, in the form of remittances sent by Indonesian labor migrants to their home regions. Therefore, the Government of Indonesia issued several regulations in the form of Laws and Presidential Regulations to regulate the sending of TKI and establish a special agency namely the National Agency for Placement and Protection of Indonesian Migrant workers (BNP2TKI) as the implementer of policies in the field of placement

and protection of overseas workers. In addition to addressing the problem of unemployment, the government's strategy in sending migrant workers abroad aims to get foreign exchange sources.

Women as Female Workers (TKW)

Women workforce took over the family's economic responsibility. Most of them work in the informal sector, working as plantation workers, domestic workers, farm workers, factory workers, scavengers, and migrant workers. The increasing number of Indonesian female migrant workers has led to a new phenomenon of feminization of migration. By looking at the types of work that the average women are involved in, it indicates that this continues the process of feminization of poverty which is a systematic process of women's poverty, where women should bear the burden due to poverty.¹⁴ The high demand for female migrant workers in the domestic sector began in the late 1970s, during which there were boom oil events in the Middle East and Saudi Arabia, so the two areas were the main target of migrant workers, including those from Indonesia. Then in 1990, migrant destination countries increased in the Asia Pacific and Southeast Asia region as a result of the opening of employment opportunities by the Government of the region.¹⁵

Based on the data on the percentage of female labor force in 1996 was 55.8% of the 517,169 migrant workers in Indonesia, in 2000 the number of female workers was 68.3% of the 435,222 Indonesian migrant workers, and in 2004 the number of female workers was 77, 9% of 380,700 Indonesian migrant workers. In 2004, the number of female migrant workers in Malaysia was fewer than the number of male migrant workers, whereas in Saudi Arabia it was the opposite, with the number of female migrant workers in Malaysia being 49%, and in Saudi Arabia 94% of the total workers recorded. The number of Indonesian migrant workers had decreased in 2005, but Indonesian migrant workers still dominate international migration.¹⁶ Until in 2007 the number of migrant workers increased again with the percentage of TKW as much as 78% of total TKI 696.746. In 2009, although the number of Indonesian labor migrants decreased slightly, TKW still dominated by 83.7% percentage of 632,172 Indonesian migrant workers (BNP2TKI 2010).¹⁷

Indonesian migrant workers are increasingly feminized and undocumented. According to IOM, almost 79% of Indonesian migrant workers are women, while BNP2TKI is lower, with a ratio of 56% for women workers and the remaining 44% to 46% being male workers. The

difference between the two sources is that data from BNP2TKI are generally based on official records, while undocumented Indonesian workers are not well documented.¹⁸ But despite the differences between the two sources of data, it remains to be seen that women working abroad remain more than men. Can be seen from the data distribution of gender-based workers presented below BNP2TKI.

Figure 1. The Distribution of Indonesian Migrant Workers based on Gender

Source: Subbid Pengolahan Data, Bidang Pengolahan dan Penyajian Data.
Distribusi TKI berdasar Jenis Kelamin. Jakarta: BNP2TKI, 2015

From the graph above can be seen that the existence of the existence of female workers or TKW abroad more than men. This is because open employment opportunities for women are greater than men, especially the types of jobs in the informal sector in households such as domestic workers, caregivers, babysitters. Not only that, the cost of travel abroad is cheaper for female workers than for male workers.¹⁹ The availability of employment opportunities for women abroad is strongly influenced by the rapid patterns of development and structural transformation that occur in the destination countries of work. The rapid economic growth and the increasing need of life in these countries became one of the causes of women participating in the job market and building careers outside the home. This raises the need for a replacement of their role in domestic affairs.²⁰ Not only that, women in destination country leave average less-skilled jobs and low salary, thus providing opportunities for migrant workers. In the case of migration of female migrant workers, low salary for the size of the destination country

are still higher than the salary in the regions of origin, thus being an important drawing factor in this migration process. Moreover, the average female workers come from the village then of course wage differences will be very visible.²¹

Factors Behind Becoming Women Migrant Workers

Lee in his theory of "Push-Pull Theory" argues that rural to urban migration is caused by rural factors and towing factors in the city. To find out the reasons for married women from villages doing international migration, the authors use the theory of Lee that immigration decisions are seen through three important factors: the driver (existing from the origin) and the attraction factor (there is a goal), as well as individual factors of migration actors.²²

Women interested in working abroad continue to increase with the following perceptions: first, give hope to get a job with high salary. Second, the destination country of work is rich countries like Arab and not hard to earn money. Third, in addition to salary also increase the experience and knowledge. Fourth, is the best way to improve the economic condition of the family. Finally, Fields for labor to earn income that can support family economic life .²³ There are two factors driving and pulling women to work; for the driving factors of wanting to dispatch a parent on a pilgrimage, wanting to repair a house/ repair a house, a very urgent need, a family problem in which the husband does not provide for the children's educational needs, the cost for children left behind with stepmother. As for the pull factor that is many jobs available, working in the rich country, can easily provide (salary), if working in Islamic countries can do umroh or hajj. When returning to the area of origin can buy land for farming and can do business development from salary earned during work.²⁴

Local Factor of Origin

The least income earned from farming and the higher rate of conversion of land to non-agriculture, as well as the narrowness of agricultural land shows the limitation or poor economically, so that the farmer households make another alternative in obtaining more income for survival by utilizing various resources. Poor farm households seek income outside agriculture. Non-formal jobs are being targeted by them, one of them being a migrant worker abroad. The new phenomenon that then emerged in rural areas, namely the lower and middle rural in the countryside able to answer the challenges of life by going abroad to work and then most of his salary sent back to their home village. Symptoms of labor mobility and

migration occurring in developing countries are a strategy to maintain the viability of farm households.²⁵

Economic Factors/ Poverty

Economic factors or poverty are the first causes that make a person choose to become a migrant worker. Because the necessities of life are so high and many costs must be spent in everyday life. If the family has a debt, then becoming a migrant worker can help pay off the accounts payable and help the family economy. The number of family dependents can be one reason to work. The more number of family dependents, the higher the time spent working. The number of family economic dependents is seen from the large number of children who are still in school and need education fees. The average number of family economic dependents based on the number of children still in school is two. Not to mention, women who are widowed with the desire to send their children to school certainly need more funds, so they inevitably have to work. The high number of married women to become migrant worker shows the demands of women to work as breadwinners to help their husbands because of dissatisfaction with their mediocre husband's income and insufficient family needs. Therefore, the magnitude of economic needs due to increasing life needs makes women decide to work abroad.

Factors that make married women work are because they have the motivation to improve the family's economy. There is an interesting fact that, today one of the reasons women work is derived from the urge of her husband to ask his wife to work abroad. Employment opportunities that are widely available abroad require a lot of workforce from women, one of which is from the domestic workers sector, which is certainly a land for female job seekers. Not only that, women in the destination country on average leave the type of work that does not require skills and low wages, thus opening up opportunities for migrant workers, especially women. Some previous studies show that in the migration process, women are generally passive migrants, meaning immigration because they follow their husbands, parents (fathers), or brothers.

There is no Land for Agriculture

The small amount of income derived from farming and the higher level of land conversion to non-agriculture, as well as the narrowing of agricultural land shows economic disability or poverty, so that farmer households make other alternatives to earn more income to survive by utilizing various resources. Poor farmer households seek income outside agriculture. Non-formal jobs are the target of them, one of them being a

migrant worker in abroad. The new phenomenon which then emerged in rural areas, namely the lower and middle levels in rural areas was able to answer the challenges of life by going abroad to work and then most of the salary was sent back to their home villages. Symptoms of mobility and labor migration that occur in developing countries are a strategy to maintain the survival of farmer households.

Interested in the Success of other Migrant Workers

When they have returned from working abroad, migrant workers choose to invest from their salary as long as migrant worker, by opening a business in their hometown such as trading (opening a stall). In addition, they are also able to finance children and help improve the family's economy and be able to socialize better than before. Some are even able to buy houses and other valuables. The success gained by migrant worker makes other people become migrant worker in abroad, hoping to become successful people like other migrant workers.

Minimum Employment and Low Wages

In fact, domestic employment opportunities are very limited while the number of labor force increases every year. Limited available employment and low wages in developing countries encourage residents to pit their fortune into developed countries even without adequate supplies (expertise, preparation, documents). It has been known that wages in other countries are higher than the country of origin, with high salaries that choose to migrate to work in other countries. Most migrant workers from developing countries are generally driven by wages that are relatively higher than the wages received in the country of origin. They prefer to work abroad with the assumption that they only want to get more work and income than they receive in their own country.

Shifting Roles

In the case of married women laborers, the crush of economic problems that require stability requires a dual role from a woman other than as a mother and wife in a family, but as a new breadwinner. Women have a responsibility for family welfare, so this also makes women participate in taking over income and family income supported by gender equality to make women begin to change roles that have been constructed by culture. Changing the role of women in the family is one of the reasons for the shift in women's opportunities to work leaving the country. The shifting role of women in the family also encourages women to work abroad to become bigger.

Women's responsiveness to families has undergone a shift, women participate in paying attention to family welfare. The family economy is no longer the responsibility of men or husbands but has been divided into joint responsibilities between husband and wife. In addition, the employment opportunities abroad are also caused by targets in the process of recruiting workers by PJTKI or brokers. This recruitment is more focused on women related to the demand for labor abroad. in accordance with the demand of foreign workers from Indonesia, Indonesian workers in general are to fill positions as informal sector workers, namely as Indonesian domestic workers and working partners who have lower selling power compared to other Asian workers. So that by working outside the country women can generate high wages, a more adequate family economy and can send their children to school.

There are several motives that are the reasons for married women to migrate. Having no agricultural land and minimal job availability for housewives especially in the village, this is a driving factor to work abroad. Especially if you do not have enough skills then it is very difficult to get a job. Some housewives work as tailors, trade, before becoming migrant workers, but their salary are still low. For women, working to help a husband is a matter of pride, but the jobs available to women in the village are limited. Low levels of education and skills do not allow them to enter a job sector that requires both. Thus, according to them being a TKI is the right decision, not to mention triggered facts / news that work abroad promising prospects and better salary.

Factors in Destination Areas

Wiyono states that pull factors for international migration are seen from their home regions, namely labor demand, geographical location, and cultural similarity. Malaysia and Singapore, its appeal is more geographically based, for Saudi Arabia more based on the desire of migrants to perform the pilgrimage, while for Hong Kong and Taiwan more based on high salary and different work experience. The availability of employment and high salary in destination countries is a major draw for rural women to migrate. This is because the main purpose of migrant workers migrating abroad is to work to help the family economy. High salary when working compared in Indonesia with the same level of education, making them prefer to work as migrant workers abroad. Such facts can be a pull factor for migrant workers in an effort to gain income in the powerlessness of their home country.²⁶

The high demand for labor in destination countries is providing opportunities for migrants to obtain employment abroad. In addition to economic factors, migrant workers choose Middle Eastern countries

because of the desire to perform the pilgrimage/ Umroh, choose Middle Eastern countries as the goal of worship, seeking experience working overseas and religious similarities with the destination. TKW chose Malaysia because of the similarity of language or ethnic that is Malay, its language is easy and almost similar to the Indonesian language. In addition, the type of work of migrant domestic workers in the destination country also influences to work abroad. The types of work the migrant worker performs while working overseas, on average working as a housekeeper, elderly care, and others are working as a tailor. The number of migrant workers who work as domestic servants, the job offered by the destination country is a housemaid. Continuing in terms of the ability of migrant workers and the level of education, being a housemaid is a job choice that does not require much skills, skills and high levels of education.

Factors of Religion and Culture

The country that is the most chosen destination for migrant worker is in the Asia Pacific region and the Middle East. The reason for choosing to become migrant worker there was due to religious factors and cultural similarities. For those who are Muslims, the Middle East region is directed by migrant worker so that all worship, because the Middle East where to carry out Hajj or Umrah, by working in the area, minimizes the expenditure of money for the costs of worship trips. While in the Asia Pacific region was chosen because of the similarity of language or ethnicity. Can be seen the similarity of Malay language with Indonesian language which is used in several countries in the Southeast Asian region. So that both of these factors (Religion and Culture) in the destination area that are valued can be a compelling factor for the mobility of labor to migrate abroad.

Wages in the Destination Country

High wages in the destination country are one of the main pulling factors for working abroad to become migrant workers. Because by working abroad can help the family economy, on the other hand abroad have high wages compared to working in their own country with the same level of education, and the high demand for jobs in the destination country provides opportunities for foreigners to get jobs abroad. Most of those who go abroad to become migrant worker are unemployed and have not worked at all, but some work as tailors, farmers or trade. On the other hand, employment opportunities abroad are still open with good wages. This reality is attractive to the workforce of a country to seek employment abroad as migrant workers.

Employment Field in the Destination Area

The increasing demand for labor in developed countries and the availability of labor in developing countries are factors that increase international migration activities. Availability of employment in the destination area from both informal and formal sectors makes some people choose to become migrant worker. However, the field of work abroad that requires a lot of labor is from the informal sector. With the high employment of the informal sector in developed countries, as well as the increasingly open employment opportunities between countries, the workforce can easily enter and enter the international labor market. By working abroad, workers will automatically become international migrants. In 2013, as many as 232 million or 3.2% of the total world population were international migrants. The large number of workers in terms of quantity that cannot be accommodated entirely by the domestic labor market requires them to look for other opportunities to work abroad.

Individual Factors of Migration Actors (Immigration Decision)

Women who emigrate internationally through struggles are not easily legally and illegally leave husband and children, resulting in many deviations experienced by social shocks. Though women workers from Indonesia with the motivation is to get a high salary for the survival of his family left behind. The results of Sriharini and Widyastiti research, Women Workers in the countries where they work are aware of household responsibilities although while they leave their households, household affairs are taken over by husbands, but their impact is very positive for their household economy. The decision to work abroad also comes from the migrant itself. There are two things that come from individual immigration agents.²⁷

Age

The results of Syarifullah's research stated that the factor that drives a person to become migrant worker is the age factor, because they think that the younger a woman is, the higher the probability, because they think that young people are more productive in work, on the other hand if someone is married considers working abroad is one way to improve the family's economy and there is also a reason that they become migrant worker because their family relationships are not harmonious so they have to be willing to go abroad to get a job.

Low Level of Education

A low level of education is also one of the factors one chooses to become a migrant worker, because they know their ability can only work in the informal sector. Especially migrant worker women working in the

informal or domestic section have the last education level of junior high school (SMP) and elementary school (SD) can work. That is, working in the informal sector is not required to have good educational standards and skills. Low educated and low education and skill, based on their job title, most also work as domestic workers and child caregivers/caretakers/caretakers, who because of the nature of their work are closely related to the high proportion of female migrant workers. The quality of migrant workers seen from formal education is still relatively low, where most of them only complete elementary school.

One of the TKW respondents named Rabiah who had worked in Hong Kong for 2 years became a babysitter, aged 25 years when she became a migrant. She is from Motui village, North Konawe District, Southeast Sulawesi. She only finished senior high school (junior high school). Then married at a young age of 17 years, a housewife with one child and husband who works motorized workshop. She chose to work abroad on the grounds that his husband's salary are not able to meet all the family's economic needs, not to mention her toddlers need formula and other baby supplies. So when she left to become a migrant worker, her son was treated by her husband assisted by her in-laws because they live at home parents. An excerpt from an interview with Rabiah explains that there is no option for him to just stay at home taking care of the household as follows:

“Rabiah: I am leaving the destination purely willing to help my husband let me have extra money and groceries. Let my husband not too heavy to bear our needs, so I am also working to help my family's economy. If the work in the village alone is less than once, at that time her husband works only in machine shop, well only tires repairing is not enough. For raising children it takes a lot of money”

For female migrant workers (who at the time of the interview are full of migrant workers), taking care of the household is not an option available. In general, they go to work abroad because of the pressures of economic needs, because the husband's income is not sufficient to meet the needs of family life. Every two months she sends money for her child's. Choice of destination country is also taken into account, according to Rabiah working in Hong Kong compared to other countries is relatively safer and salary is also higher.

Among all female migrant workers working abroad are mostly married women compared with unmarried and from rural areas. Many factors that support married women to work overseas. Not a few working women who help the husband for the sake of the economy of his family. A married woman has a complex role, namely as a wife and a housewife. A married woman becomes a migrant worker to help her husband earn a living, while

an unmarried woman or widow becomes a TKW to help her family's economy. In terms of responsibility, married women have a greater responsibility than unmarried women, having to leave their husbands and children. The large number married women who prefer to work outside the country. Viewed from the table below describes migrants who work with higher marital status.

Table 1. Indonesian Labor Placement Based on Marriage Status Period 2016 and 2017 (Till October)

NO	BULAN	2016				2017			
		Kawin	Belum Kawin	Cerai	Total	Kawin	Belum Kawin	Cerai	Total
1	Januari	11.931 50%	10.221 43%	1.513 6%	23.665	7.711 45%	5.861 34%	3.427 20%	16.999
2	Februari	9.313 53%	6.979 40%	1.157 7%	17.449	8.069 41%	6.490 33%	5.182 26%	19.741
3	Maret	10.337 51%	8.396 43%	1.387 7%	20.12	9.711 44%	8.308 37%	4.211 19%	22.230
4	April	9.716 51%	7.904 42%	1.315 7%	18.935	8.668 45%	6.690 35%	3.871 20%	19.229
5	Mei	9.786 51%	7.926 42%	1.386 7%	19.098	9.166 41%	7.711 35%	5.559 25%	22.496
6	Juni	10.432 52%	7.948 40%	1.698 8%	20.078	8.385 43%	7.640 39%	3.696 19%	19.721
7	Juli	8.561 54%	5.699 36%	1.661 10%	15.921	11.969 50%	9.799 41%	2.058 9%	23.826
8	Agustus	10.998 52%	8.546 40%	1.791 8%	21.335	10.237 49%	8.905 43%	1.714 8%	20.856
9	September	9.494 50%	7.674 41%	1.676 9%	18.844	8.943 51%	6.811 41%	1.338 8%	16.642
10	Oktober	9.995 50%	8.453 42%	1.653 8%	21.101	9.399 51%	7.449 41%	1.501 8%	18.349
Total		100.563 51%	79.746 41%	15.237 8%	195.546	91.908 46%	75.724 38%	32.557 16%	2000.089
Selisih (Turun/Naik)		Kawin 2016 & 2017		-8.755	T	Belum Kawin 2016 % 2017		-4.022	T
		Cerai 2016 & 2017		17,320	N				

Print Period Date 06 November 2017

Data source: Center for Research on Development and Information (PUSLITFO BNP2TKI)

Note:

Q: Number of Placements in 2017 Declining Compared to 2016

N: Placement Amount 2017 Increased Increase Compared to 2016

From the table above can be seen that in two periods of 2016-2017 the number of migrant male and female workers who have married have a high percentage compared with unmarried status or divorced status. This is because they have a big responsibility in the form of cost of living necessities to their families in the area of origin. Broadly speaking for married women

working overseas due to the economic demands of the family, only a few work with other motivations such as prestige, leisure time, improved status of husbands, family and society. However, there are four important factors underlying the migration decision of married women to work abroad, namely age, husband's income level, family dependence, and education level.

First age, the greater the working population or the number of workers and the greater the labor force participation rate, and the greater the number of the workforce. Although the population growth can be suppressed but the supply of labor is getting higher as more and more people enter working age, hence the supply of labor will also increase. The relationship between the migrant worker program abroad and the age, ie the government has set a requirement, which is at least 18 years of age or as required by the destination country (article 39 paragraph 2/ MEN/ 2002), in which the age is mature enough and mature in attitude and high morale. Second is the level of income of husbands where the salary of the husband is not able to meet the needs of households, so inevitably the wife helped to finance by working. The average head of the migrant worker family works as a laborer/ construction worker, works as a farmer, works in a garage, as a trader/ self-employed as a driver, others work with fixed salary such as security guards, cooperative employees, and teachers. In addition to basic work, there are several heads of families who have side jobs or double jobs, namely in the field of services and construction workers. Uncertainty of husband's income, requires the wife to take part in increasing husband's income.²⁸

Third is the factor of the number of dependents of the family, with the number of family members more, then the dependent on the fulfillment of daily household needs is also greater. With conditions like this then the husband needs the help of energy in earning a living, then the wife also took part in working. The number of family dependents can be one reason women work to decide whether to work or stay home to play their domestic role. The more the number of family dependents, the higher the amount of time a woman spends to work. The number of family economic dependents is seen from the large number of children who are still in school and need the cost of education. The average numbers of family TKW households based on the number of children who are still in school are two people.²⁹ The fourth factor is the level of education, the vast majority of women migrant workers with low education and employment available abroad are informal sectors so they do not require educational qualifications at work. In addition, the salary on offer even though the informal sector remains larger than the salary received when working domestically. This is what makes married women prefer to work overseas.³⁰ Low-skilled and low-skill

educational, mostly based on job titles, mostly work as domestic workers and caregivers / caretakers, who because of the nature of their work is closely related to the high proportion of female migrant workers. The quality of migrant workers is seen from the formal education of TKW relatively low, where most of them only finish elementary school.

Migration as a Family Lives Strategy

The implementation of the livelihood strategy according to Scoones provides three possible livelihood strategies by farmers' households, namely: 1) agricultural livelihoods engineering, which utilizes the agricultural sector efficiently and effectively by adding external inputs such as technology and manpower work (intensification), or expanding arable land (extensivication); 2) multiple livelihood patterns (diversification), is applying diversity of livelihood patterns by finding other employment in addition to agriculture or by increasing the working members of the family (father, mother, child) to work to increase income; 3) spatial or migratory engineering, that is, efforts made by utilizing mobility to other areas outside their village, whether permanently or circularly to obtain or income streams.³¹

In the study of livelihood strategies, the involvement and contribution of women in earning a living by being migrant workers is a form of compulsion due to the inability of the head of the household to act as a breadwinner for the family. When the head of the family is unable to raise the family economy, the boys, girls, or wife become other breadwinners. This mechanism is known as a survival strategy that explains that migration is one strategy among other strategies.³² For households, sending their family members to work in other areas and performing non-permanent mobility has a lower poor probability than those who stayer.³³ Being a TKW, means being able to generate income and help the husband in earning a living for the family. This is a pride for women for being able to send their children to a higher level.

Conclusion

International migration is a phenomenon that occurs in almost every country. Until now, the number continues to increase and dominated by women who work in the domestic sector. The female workforce consists of unmarried women, married women, and widows working for the same goal of economic issues. However, the results of the study indicate that women with the status of get married at most as a migrant worker in overseas, with the most dominant reason that is economic needs with the intention for family resilience.

There are several reasons that affect women to migrate. There are driving factors and pull factors, and the reason for the incidents of the migrants themselves. Driving factors originated from the area of origin that is the narrowness of agricultural land in the area of origin and the unavailability of employment in the area of origin, the pull factor of the destination area is influenced by the availability of employment in destination areas with high salary, and the desire of the lack of choice of individual migration actors is women with skills and low education besides immigrating as women labor in overseas.

Endnotes

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² Hidayatunnismah, dkk. 2013. *Migrasi Internasional Tenaga Kerja Perempuan dan Human Trafficking*. Jakarta: Universitas Indonesia.

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⁷ Todaro, 1978.

⁸ Lee E. 1984. Suatu teori migrasi. (Alih bahasa dari bahasa Inggris oleh Hans Daeng). Yogyakarta [ID]: Pusat Penelitian Kependudukan UGM.

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¹¹ Lee E., *op. cit.*

¹² Raharto, Aswatini. 2017. *Pengambilan Keputusan Tenaga Kerja Indonesia (TKI) Perempuan untuk Bekerja di Luar Negeri: Kasus Kabupaten Cilacap*. Pusat Penelitian Kependudukan – LIPI.

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²³ Nurjannah, Siti. 2008. *Perspektif Migran Wanita*. Jurnal Penelitian Universitas Mataram. Vol 2 No.11

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³⁰ Novita, *op. cit.*

³¹ Scoones I. 1998. Sustainable rural livelihoods a framework for analysis, IDS Working Paper 72, Brighton: IDS.

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